

WALNUT

factsheet

BRINE

Brine to value

Introduction

Seawater desalination is one of the primary methods for addressing water scarcity. As global freshwater consumption increases by approximately 1% each year, desalination has become an increasingly attractive option for freshwater production. However, a major drawback of this process is the discharge of brine into the sea or other surface water bodies, which can negatively impact the surrounding environment.

Brines produced from seawater or groundwater desalination—as well as those generated as by-products of industrial processes—contain valuable elements such as magnesium (Mg) and potassium (K). These elements can be recovered and used in various applications, including as micronutrients in fertilizers. Brines may also contain sulfates and calcium, which are valuable to the fertilizer industry. In addition to recovering these minerals in the form of salts, the remaining sodium chloride (NaCl) can be extracted and used in multiple industrial applications. Furthermore, advanced treatment methods can recover distilled water, which is suitable for use in irrigation and industrial processes.

Technology

The brine treatment process starts with **two precipitation steps**. First, **magnesium is removed by adding sodium hydroxide** (NaOH) to the brine, leading to the **precipitation and recovery of magnesium hydroxide** [Mg(OH)₂]. The resulting supernatant (magnesium-free stream) is treated with sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃) in a second tank to **precipitate calcium carbonate** (CaCO₃). The resulting solids are solar-dried, while **the supernatant**, after **neutralisation with hydrochloric acid** (HCl), **enters nanofiltration** (NF).

The NF unit separates divalent from monovalent ions, optimising ion rejection and permeate recovery. Sodium sulfate (Na₂SO₄) is recovered from the concentrated stream via solar drying, while the permeate proceeds to the next stage, then treated in a multi-effect distillation (MED) evaporator under vacuum, yielding a concentrated stream and recovered distilled water.

The concentrated stream is fed into a crystallisation unit, recovering distilled water and a slurry with sodium (Na), chloride (Cl), and potassium (K), then processed in a flotation unit, where potassium chloride (KCl) is separated from sodium chloride (NaCl) using surfactants and air agitation, ensuring **effective mineral separation**. Both undergo solar precipitation, **completing the Zero Liquid Discharge** (ZLD) process.

 PROCESS
 PRODUCT

Characteristics

The treatment train is fully containerised, designed for nutrient recovery and brine treatment. This modular setup enables easy transport, installation and operation in diverse environments. All critical processes are integrated within a controlled environment to optimise the use of space, safety and efficiency.

The process treatment has an overall capacity of 500L/batch and can treat up to 6 batches per day. The composition of seawater brine from the desalination process includes 35,400 mg/L Cl^- , 19,647 mg/L Na^+ , 3,820 mg/L SO_4^{2-} , 2,735 mg/L Mg^{2+} , 1,552 mg/L Ca^{2+} , 831 mg/L K^+ , and 238 mg/L HCO_3^- .

The first step of the process operated with high recoveries of Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} ions. The first precipitation unit achieved 95% Mg recovery with a purity up to 98% and the second precipitation unit 94% Ca recovery with a purity up to 98%.

The NF unit showcased high rejection rates of divalent ions, such as Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and SO_4^{2-} . Specifically, sulphate rejection consistently exceeded 99.8%, while calcium rejection reached 85% and magnesium 94%.

The crystalliser unit concentrated effectively the MED outflow stream 2.5 times, resulting in a slurry and a stream of distilled water with TDS up to 5.2 mg/L.

From the final step of the process (flotation unit) more than 90% for potassium (K) and more than 92% of sodium were recovered with 81% purity for KCl and 99.6% purity for NaCl salts.

The MED evaporator unit reached high concentration factor (CF) and water recovery up to 75% and high ion removal to the recovered distilled water with TDS up to 4.8 mg/L.

Field test

The recovered salts (KCl , CaCO_3 , $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$) from the brine desalination pilot plant enhance plant growth and perform equivalently to commercial fertilisers when applied at proper rates. Magnesium is vital for chlorophyll synthesis and enzymatic activation; calcium supports cell wall structure and membrane stability, and potassium regulates osmosis and photosynthesis. In soil-less systems, they improved biomass and mitigated biotic stress. Since these systems are highly sensitive to nutrient solubility and ionic balance, the absence of growth reduction or deficiency symptoms confirms their stability and suitability for hydroponics. However, application rates must be precisely managed, as all three salts - $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$, KCl , and CaCO_3 - are saline in nature. Overuse can increase electrical conductivity (EC), disrupt osmotic balance, and lead to salt stress symptoms, as reduced biomass, chlorosis, leaf burn, and inhibited root elongation.

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Credits

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